

NEUROCOGNITIVE AND BIOCHEMICAL ALTERATIONS INDUCED BY PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCES (ALCOHOL AND MARIJUANA) UNDER SUB-CHRONIC STRESS CONDITIONS IN MICE

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ABSTRACT

Background: Sub-chronic stress and substance abuse are major contributors to cognitive deficits and neurobiological dysfunction. This study investigated the effects of marijuana and alcohol, individually and in combination with stress, on cognitive performance and biochemical markers in mice. **Aim.** To determine the effects of physical stress with psychoactive substances (alcohol and marijuana) on cognitive performance and biochemical indices. **Methods:** Sixty four (64) male mice were randomly divided into eight groups (n = 8): Group 1 – Normal Saline (NS), Group 2 – Stressors only (SR: restraint and sleep deprivation via music), Group 3 – Marijuana (CB), Group 4 – CB + SR, Group 5 – Alcohol (AC), Group 6 – AC + SR, Group 7 – CB + AC, and Group 8 – CB + AC + SR. Stress was induced for 31 days, after which treatments were administered for 7 days. Spatial learning and memory were assessed using the Morris Water Maze (MWM). Biochemical analyses for corticosterone and oxidative stress markers

(malondialdehyde MDA, superoxide dismutase SOD) were performed following sub chronic-stress induction. **Results:** Mice in the CB + SR ($p < 0.03$), AC + SR ($p < 0.01$), and

CB + AC + SR ($p < 0.01$) groups exhibited significantly prolonged escape latencies in the MWM compared to the SR group, indicating impaired spatial memory. There was also marked elevated serum corticosterone levels and increased oxidative stress markers (MDA and SOD) were observed in all stressed groups, with the significant alterations in the CB + AC + SR group ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** Combined exposure to sub chronic-stress and psychoactive substances, particularly alcohol and marijuana, synergistically impairs spatial memory and induces neuroendocrine and oxidative stress. These findings highlight the compounded risks of concurrent substance use and sub-chronic stress on cognitive and physiological functions.

KEYWORD: Marijuana; Alcohol; Psychoactive-substances; Sub-chronic; Neurocognitive; Biochemical.

INTRODUCTION

Stress, particularly when sustained over time, represents a significant threat to physical and mental health. While the physiological stress response is adaptive and essential for survival, chronic or repeated exposure can produce maladaptive changes in brain function, behaviour, and systemic physiology. These changes have been implicated in various neuropsychiatric disorders, including anxiety, depression, and cognitive decline (McEwen, 2007). The rising global use of psychoactive substances, especially alcohol and cannabis (marijuana), among individuals exposed to chronic stress adds another layer of complexity to public health concerns. When co-exposure to stress and substances occurs, as often observed in real-life scenarios, their interactions may amplify detrimental neurobiological and behavioural outcomes (Sinha, 2008).

Animal models have become indispensable tools in understanding the pathophysiology of stress and its interplay with substance abuse. In particular, rodent models offer a controlled means of exploring how sub-chronic stress alters cognitive and biochemical functions, especially when combined with substances like alcohol and marijuana. The Morris Water Maze (MWM) is a well-validated behavioural tool widely used to assess spatial learning and memory, particularly hippocampus-dependent cognitive processes (Vorhees & Williams, 2006). In parallel, biochemical markers such as corticosterone (the rodent equivalent of cortisol) and oxidative stress indices provide insight into the systemic and neurochemical responses to stress and substance exposure.

This study aims to explore how sub-chronic stress modulates cognitive performance and neurobiological responses when combined with psychoactive substances, alcohol and marijuana. Understanding these interactions is vital, given the increasing co-use of alcohol and cannabis among stressed populations, especially young adults, and the rising burden of cognitive disorders.

Stress activates the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, leading to the release of glucocorticoids such as corticosterone in rodents (Sapolsky *et al.*, 2000). While short-term stress can enhance certain types of memory, sustained glucocorticoid elevation has been linked to hippocampal damage, impaired synaptic plasticity, and cognitive deficits (Joëls *et al.*, 2006). The hippocampus, due to its high density of glucocorticoid receptors, is particularly vulnerable to the effects of chronic stress.

In rodents, various stress paradigms have been developed to simulate human-like stress conditions. Among them, sub-chronic stress models (21-day restraint or sleep deprivation protocols) are commonly employed to represent sustained but not permanent stress states, allowing the study of preclinical progression toward cognitive and biochemical dysfunction (Willner, 2017).

Repeated stress exposure disrupts hippocampal function, reduces brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), impairs neurogenesis, and increases oxidative stress (Marques *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, chronic or sub-chronic stress enhances the vulnerability of brain structures to further damage, particularly when combined with neurotoxic substances like alcohol and cannabis (Willner, 2017).

Despite the high prevalence of concurrent alcohol and cannabis use, limited studies have investigated their combined neurocognitive effects, particularly under stress conditions. Co-use of alcohol and cannabis has been shown to produce additive or even synergistic impairments in memory, attention, and psychomotor function in both human and animal models (Hartman & Huestis, 2013). These impairments are thought to result from interactions at the level of neurotransmitter systems, including GABA, glutamate, and the endocannabinoid system.

Cognitive deficits observed in stress and substance models are often linked with oxidative stress. Oxidative stress results from an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS)

production and antioxidant defences. In the brain, this imbalance leads to damage to lipids, proteins, and DNA, contributing to synaptic dysfunction and neurodegeneration (Pham-Huy *et al.*, 2008).

Malondialdehyde (MDA) is a common marker of lipid peroxidation, while enzymes like superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) reflect the status of endogenous antioxidant defense. Elevated MDA levels and reduced SOD activity have been observed in both chronic stress and alcohol models (Das & Vasudevan, 2007).

Corticosterone is the primary glucocorticoid in rodents and serves as a reliable biomarker of stress. Prolonged elevation of corticosterone reflects HPA axis dysregulation and is associated with impaired hippocampal function and memory deficits. Substance use, particularly alcohol and THC, can further elevate corticosterone levels, compounding stress-induced neuroendocrine disruption (Roozendaal *et al.*, 2006).

Thus, biochemical assays of corticosterone and oxidative stress markers provide a mechanistic link between behavioral deficits and underlying neurobiological changes.

Rationale for the Study. Although both stress and psychoactive substance use independently contribute to cognitive and neurobiological dysfunction, the combined effects of sub-chronic stress with alcohol and cannabis have not been thoroughly examined in animal models. Given the growing prevalence of co-use of these substances—often in high-stress environments such as among students, soldiers, or individuals with mental health disorders—it is essential to understand how these exposures interact to influence cognitive health.

Moreover, the use of a murine model allows controlled manipulation of stress and drug exposure, as well as precise measurement of behavioural and biochemical outcomes. By incorporating assessments of corticosterone and oxidative stress markers alongside cognitive testing, this study aims to provide a comprehensive picture of how stress and substance use affect brain function.

METHODOLOGY

Ethical Considerations

The present study, titled "*Neurocognitive and Biochemical Alterations Induced by Psychoactive Substances (Alcohol and Marijuana) under Sub-Chronic Stress Conditions in Mice*," was conducted in strict accordance with internationally accepted ethical guidelines for

animal research. Ethical integrity was central to the conduct of this study. Every effort was made to adhere to the 3Rs principle (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) in animal research. The study's design ensured that the scientific benefits outweighed potential ethical concerns, and that animal welfare was prioritized at every stage according to "The National Research Council's Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (8th Edition, 2011)".

Experimental Animals

A total of 64 adult male mice (weighing 25–30 g, aged 8–10 weeks) were procured from a registered animal breeding facility. The animals were housed in groups of eight per cage under standard laboratory conditions: temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), humidity (50–60%), and a 12 h light/dark cycle. They had free access to standard rodent chow and clean water *ad libitum*. The mice were acclimatized for 7 days before the commencement of the experiment.

All procedures were conducted in accordance with the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (8th Edition, 2011) and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) of the department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Niger Delta university, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State.

Experimental Design

The mice were randomly divided into eight groups ($n = 8$ per group):

- Group 1 (NS) – Normal saline, no stress (control)
- Group 2 (SR) – Sub-chronic stress (restraint + sleep deprivation via music)
- Group 3 (CB) – Marijuana only (no stress)
- Group 4 (CB + SR) – Marijuana + sub-chronic stress
- Group 5 (AC) – Alcohol only (no stress)
- Group 6 (AC + SR) – Alcohol + sub-chronic stress
- Group 7 (AC + CB) – Alcohol + marijuana (no stress)
- Group 8 (AC + CB + SR) – Alcohol + marijuana + sub-chronic stress

Sub-Chronic Stress Induction

Sub-chronic stress was induced for 31 consecutive days using a combination of:

- Restraint stress: Each mouse was placed in a well-ventilated restraining tube for 2 hours per day (adapted from Buynitsky & Mostofsky, 2009).
- Sleep deprivation via music: Loud, irregular music (~85–100 dB) was played throughout the dark phase to disrupt sleep cycles (adapted from Zubidat *et al.*, 2011).

These stressors were alternated daily to minimize habituation and increase stress unpredictability.

Drug Preparation and Administration

- Alcohol (ethanol) was diluted in distilled water to a concentration of 10% v/v and administered orally at 2 g/kg/day (Crews & Nixon, 2009).
- Marijuana extract: Cannabis *sativa* dried leaves were obtained and authenticated. The ethanolic extract was prepared using rotary extraction techniques and administered at a dose of 500 mg/kg/day, based on previous behavioural studies (Cha et al., 2006).

Treatments were administered orally by gavage for 7 consecutive days, beginning immediately after the 31-day stress induction period. The control group received equivalent volumes of normal saline.

Morris Water Maze Test (MWM)

The Morris Water Maze was used to assess spatial learning and memory after the 7-day treatment period (Vorhees & Williams, 2006).

- Apparatus: A circular pool (120 cm diameter, 50 cm height) filled with opaque water ($25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) to a depth of 30 cm. A hidden platform (10 cm diameter) was submerged 1 cm below the water surface in the northeast quadrant.
- Acquisition trials (Day 1–4): Each mouse underwent four trials per day for 4 days. The starting position was varied, but the platform location remained constant. Escape latency (time to find the platform) was recorded.
- Probe trial (Day 5): The platform was removed, and each mouse was allowed to swim freely for 60 seconds. Time spent in the target quadrant was recorded to assess memory retention. Behaviour was recorded using a video-tracking system, and results were analyzed offline.

Biochemical Assays

Following behavioural assessments, the mice were anesthetized and euthanized. Blood was collected via cardiac puncture, and brains were quickly excised. The hippocampus was dissected out for biochemical analysis.

a. Corticosterone Measurement

- Serum corticosterone levels were determined using a commercially available ELISA kit (Abcam, UK), following the manufacturer's instructions.
- Results were expressed in ng/mL.

b. Oxidative Stress Markers

Brain homogenates were prepared in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and the following oxidative stress markers were evaluated:

- Malondialdehyde (MDA): Measured as an index of lipid peroxidation using the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) assay (Ohkawa et al., 1979).
- Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) activity: Assessed using the method described by Misra & Fridovich (1972).
- Catalase (CAT) activity: Determined following Aebi's method (1984). All values were expressed per mg protein using Bradford protein assay.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test was used to compare differences among groups. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism (version 8.2).

RESULTS

In the Morris Water Maze test, the stressor-only group (SR, 10 ml/kg) showed a significant increase in escape latency and a reduction in time spent in the target quadrant, indicating pronounced cognitive impairment due to sub-chronic exposure to restraint stress and music-induced sleep deprivation, (Figure 1 and 2). Treatment with Cannabis (CB, 500 mg/kg) and Alcohol (AC, 0.02%) in combination with the stressors further exacerbated memory deficits, as reflected by longer escape latencies and less time spent in the target quadrant compared to the SR, (10 ml/kg) negative control group (Figure 1 and 2). The control group (NS) demonstrated optimal spatial learning and memory performance, with shorter escape latencies and increased time in the target quadrant, confirming intact cognitive function. Together, these findings suggest that sub-chronic stress impairs cognitive function, and this impairment is worsened by exposure to marijuana and alcohol, supporting the synergistic detrimental effects of psychoactive substances under sub-chronic stress conditions on hippocampal-dependent memory functions (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Effect of Psychoactive Substances (Alcohol and Marijuana) under Sub-Chronic Stress Conditions in cognitive behaviour using MWM (escape latency). NS (10 ml/kg): Normal Saline, SR (10 ml/kg): Stressor (restraint + music-induced sleep deprivation), CB (500 mg/kg): Marijuana, AC (0.02%): Alcohol, * $p < 0.001$ compared to SR (#) group, **** $p < 0.0001$ compared with SR (#) group**

Figure 2: Effect of Psychoactive Substances (Alcohol and Marijuana) under Sub-Chronic Stress Conditions in cognitive behaviour using MWM (Target quadrant) : NS (10 ml/kg): Normal Saline, SR (10 ml/kg): Stressor (restraint + music-induced sleep deprivation), CB (500 mg/kg): Marijuana, AC (0.02%): Alcohol, * $p < 0.03$ compared to SR (#) group, * $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$ compared with SR (#) group.**

Sub-chronic exposure to combined stressors restraint and music-induced sleep deprivation led to significant biochemical alterations in mice. The stressor group (SR, 10 ml/kg) exhibited a marked elevation in plasma corticosterone levels, indicating activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis in response to prolonged stress (Figure 3). Additionally, malondialdehyde (MDA) levels were significantly increased, reflecting enhanced lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress (Figure 4). Concurrently, there was a notable reduction in the antioxidant enzymes, superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT), suggesting impaired oxidative defence mechanisms (Figure 5 and Figure 6). In groups treated with marijuana (CB, 500 mg/kg) and alcohol (AC, 0.02%) alongside the stressors.

There was a further significant increase in corticosterone and MDA levels compared to the SR group, indicating a synergistic exacerbation of stress-induced endocrine and oxidative responses (Figure 3 and 4). Conversely, SOD and CAT activities were further suppressed, highlighting an intensified redox imbalance due to the combined effect of psychoactive substances and stress (Figure 5 and 6). The normal saline (NS, 10 ml/kg) control group maintained baseline levels of all biochemical parameters, confirming the physiological norm and the disruptive influence of the experimental interventions (Figure 3-6).

Figure 3: Effect of Psychoactive Substances (Alcohol and Marijuana) under Sub-Chronic Stress Conditions in biochemical marker (corticosterone). NS (10 ml/kg): Normal Saline, SR (10 ml/kg): Stressor (restraint + music-induced sleep deprivation), CB (500 mg/kg): Marijuana, AC (0.02%): Alcohol, * $p < 0.03$ compared to SR (#) group, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.001$ compared with SR (#) group.**

Figure 4: Effect of Psychoactive Substances (Alcohol and Marijuana) under Sub-Chronic Stress Conditions in biochemical marker (MDA). NS (10 ml/kg): Normal Saline, SR (10 ml/kg): Stressor (restraint + music-induced sleep deprivation), CB (500 mg/kg): Marijuana, AC (0.02%): Alcohol, * $p < 0.03$ compared to SR (#) group, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared with SR (#) group.

Figure 5: Effect of Psychoactive Substances (Alcohol and Marijuana) under Sub-Chronic Stress Conditions in biochemical marker (SOD). NS (10 ml/kg): Normal Saline, SR (10 ml/kg): Stressor (restraint + music-induced sleep deprivation), CB (500 mg/kg):

Marijuana, AC (0.02%): Alcohol, * $p < 0.03$ compared to SR (#) group, *** $p < 0.001$ compared with SR (#) group.

Figure 6: Effect of Psychoactive Substances (Alcohol and Marijuana) under Sub-Chronic Stress Conditions in biochemical marker (CAT). NS (10 ml/kg): Normal Saline, SR (10 ml/kg): Stressor (restraint + music-induced sleep deprivation), CB (500 mg/kg): Marijuana, AC (0.02%): Alcohol, * $p < 0.03$ compared to SR (#) group, ** $p < 0.01$ compared with SR (#) group.

DISCUSSION

The current findings demonstrate that exposure to psychoactive substances such as alcohol and marijuana under sub-chronic stress conditions induces significant cognitive deficits and oxidative stress, as reflected in both behavioural and biochemical markers in this study (Figure 1-6). These observations can be pharmacologically explained by the synergistic neurotoxic effects of stress and psychoactive agents on the central nervous system (CNS). Sub-chronic stress, particularly from restraint and sleep deprivation, activates the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, elevating glucocorticoid levels (notably corticosterone in rodents), which can impair hippocampal function and neurogenesis, critical for spatial learning and memory (McEwen, 2007). In this study, the stress-only group (SR) showed impaired cognitive performance on the Morris Water Maze (MWM) test, evidenced by increased escape latency and reduced time spent in the target quadrant (Figure 1 and 2). This aligns with previous reports linking stress-induced corticosterone elevation to spatial

memory deficits (Joëls *et al.*, 2011). The co-exposure to alcohol (AC) and marijuana (CB) under stress intensified cognitive impairments. Alcohol, a CNS depressant, modulates GABAergic and glutamatergic neurotransmission and disrupts hippocampal long-term potentiation (LTP), a key mechanism underlying learning and memory (White *et al.*, 2000). Chronic alcohol consumption has been shown to impair neuroplasticity and exacerbate stress-induced HPA axis dysregulation (Herman & Cullinan, 1997), which may explain the significant behavioural deficits observed. Marijuana, particularly its psychoactive compound Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (THC), acts via cannabinoid receptor type 1 (CB1) in the brain, modulating neurotransmitter release. Under stress, the endocannabinoid system becomes dysregulated, and exogenous THC may further impair synaptic function and memory processes (Riebe & Wotjak, 2011). THC has been reported to impair working memory and disrupt neural oscillations necessary for learning and cognition (Ranganathan & D'Souza, 2006). Biochemically, the significant elevation in corticosterone, malondialdehyde (MDA), and suppression of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) in the treated groups indicate oxidative stress and compromised redox homeostasis (Figure 3-6). Both alcohol and cannabis promote reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, contributing to lipid peroxidation (as reflected by increased MDA) and depletion of antioxidant defences (Marselos & Bakiri, 1999; Das & Vasudevan, 2007). This oxidative environment facilitates neuronal damage, synaptic loss, and functional impairments in cognitive circuits. Overall, the findings underscore a pharmacological interaction wherein sub-chronic stress primes the brain for heightened vulnerability to substance-induced neurotoxicity. The combined effects of HPA axis overactivation and oxidative damage culminate in severe cognitive deficits. These results emphasize the need for neuroprotective interventions that target oxidative stress and HPA dysregulation, such as antioxidant therapy or adaptogenic agents derived from medicinal plants. Future directions may involve exploring the neuroprotective roles of plant-based compounds with antioxidant and anxiolytic properties to counteract these stress-substance interactions, particularly in contexts relevant to African health burdens.

CONCLUSION

This study comprehensively investigated the neurocognitive and biochemical impacts of psychoactive substances, alcohol and marijuana applied under sub-chronic stress conditions in mice, using behavioural and biochemical parameters as endpoints. The findings offer compelling evidence of a synergistic interaction between sub-chronic stress and psychoactive

substance exposure, leading to marked alterations in brain function and biochemistry. These results underscore the neurobiological risks associated with psychoactive substance use, especially under conditions of sub-chronic stress. This has important translational implications for understanding the vulnerability of human populations particularly adolescents and young adults who may simultaneously experience psychosocial stress and engage in substance use. Future studies should further explore the molecular pathways underlying these interactions and evaluate potential therapeutic strategies to mitigate such combined neurotoxic effects.

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